

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CONTEH****FIRST NAME: THEKEKA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction
2. The stepwise approach to academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
3. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have carefully read the coursepack on International Academic writing, denoted as ACA-401D. The course provided comprehensive details on critical points that must be considered in writing an academic paper or book.

The content has enhanced my knowledge of the fundamentals of the English language with a refresher on punctuation, style of writing, and a clear guide on the do's and don't of academic writing. This, to me, has served as a foundation or the pillar on which my writing skills will be improved and a resource for my thesis, as well as reports of research.

The quality of material provided by EUCLID for ACA-401D changed my perception of the thoroughness of the course structure and design. I have inculcated a sense of commitment and focus on academic work to meet the requirement.

My response paper for ACA-401D will present the stepwise approach to academic essay writing, with details on the structure of academic essay and basic guidelines on

punctuation. A brief on the writing style will be discussed, and an emphasis on plagiarism will be outstanding.

2) THE STEPWISE APPROACH OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

An academic essay is a piece of writing that develops an idea or argument using evidence, analysis, and interpretation.

Though many types of essays may be written, as a student, the content and length of an essay will depend on the level of the student, subject of study, and course requirements. However, most essays at the university level are argumentative. They aim to persuade readers of a particular position or perspective on a topic. Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2021, 7). The academic essay includes, among others, research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference papers; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations.

In writing an academic essay, the author needs to note that the essay should focus on providing an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.

It is important to carry out an academic essay following the approach I called the stepwise approach to academic writing. This stepwise approach involves:

- Researching the essay topic
- Organizing your ideas
- Writing the essay
- Referencing the essay
- Editing the essay
- Handing the essay in

The student or author should consider it imperative to read and thoroughly research on what to write. This will provide the knowledge and evidence to develop the thesis and answers. It is advisable to always keep notes of relevant information that will contribute to the essay writing.

In addition to the reading and research process, academic essay writing requires creative and critical thinking to have broadened ideas on the topic as well as to narrow the focus or scope of ideas of the subject matter. However, it is worth noting that a well-balanced essay is written with inputs from a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key argument and relevant aspect of the topic.

After having a better understanding of the topic, there is then the need to write and essay plans to answer to the questions and have a structure for the essay.

The next step involves actually putting the ideas in writing. The essay writing will focus on three components:

1. Introduction
2. Body
3. Conclusion

The first thing to do in this stage is to produce a draft according to the structure and framework of the essay. The detail of the essay will become much easier once the draft is available.

Referencing is the next stage that goes along with essay writing, as all academic essays must contain references. **It is only referenced to guard against plagiarism, a serious academic crime.** “It is necessary that you inquire and understand the referencing style of the faculty, school, or journal. Some will provide guidance on the referencing standard they prefer” (EUCLID 2021, 11).

The next two stages have to do with the editing the essay and handing the essay in. The editing process will primarily check on the overall structure of the essay to determine if it has a clear introduction, body, and conclusion; ensure that each paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument; and make sure the words used to mean what you think they mean, as well as checking on punctuation and spelling.

“Essays get dramatically improved upon careful editing. An essay is often recommended to be kept aside for a few days before editing. This practice gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your essay with a fresh perspective. If you find that you need more information or there are deficiencies in your arguments, be focused and calm in fixing the problem” (EUCLID 2021, 11).

The last stage is to hand in the essay. In doing so, you must be sure you submit on or before the due date, be sure where and to whom the essay should be submitted, ensure the essay is formatted correctly.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

The structure of academic essays is very significant in presenting the idea and response to the questions related to the topic. The University of Birmingham in their book: A short guide to essay planning and structure mentions the following:

The purpose of an essay is to present a logical, reasoned argument in response to a specific question. An effective structure helps your argument to unfold clearly to the reader. You want your response to be focussed and progressive, rather than just a jumble of ideas.

On this background, the structure of an essay must contain an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction part of an essay starts from a general view of the idea and narrows down to specific. The topic area is introduced with a general broad opening sentence. It should answer the questions with a thesis statement and provide the essay's summary or road map. According to the University of Arizona Global Campus Campus Writing Center:

An introduction is the first paragraph of your paper. The goal of your introduction is to let your reader know the topic of the paper and what points will be made about the topic. The thesis statement that is included in the introduction tells your reader the specific purpose or main argument of your paper. These can be achieved by taking your introduction from general to specific.

Moving from a general subject to a specific thesis will provide the readers a better understanding of what your essay will focus on.

The body is the next part of the essay structure that presents the knowledge and evidence to back your ideas “The body of your essay consists of paragraphs. Each is a building block in the construction of your argument” (EUCLID 2021, 10). The body is where you show the following:

- Answers the question by developing a discussion
- Show your knowledge and grasp of the material you have read
- Offer exposition and evidence to develop your argument
- Use relevant examples and authoritative quotes

However, where the question has more than one or two parts, the body should be structured into sections, with each section dealing with one part of the question.

An academic conclusion paragraph reminds your reader of the main points of your paper and summarizes the significance of the conversation. The conclusion moves from specific to general. It should: restate your answer to the question, re-summarize the main points and; include a final, broad statement (about possible implications and future directions for research to qualify the conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10).

4) **STYLE GUIDES**

A writing style guide is a document that sets standard writing, grammar, and punctuation conventions for a particular organization in an effort to maintain a consistent tone and style regardless of how many content contributors are on the team. “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Generally, style manuals include everything a writer needs to know to make their work look and read just like every other work written in that style — the look of the page, the way other authors are referenced in the body of the work, and even the tone of the writing (Purdue University, n.d.).

Many academic institutions and publications require the use of style guides. A clarity and consistency framework is provided by the style guide. Guide on formatting, like how citations, footnotes, and margins look, and the tone's formality are specified. The guide helps maintain consistency, especially for published works and can help writers produce content that meets certain academic publishing requirements.

There are various types of style guides. These four most common writing style guides are:

1. Modern Language Association Handbook
2. Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association
3. Associated Press Stylebook
4. Chicago Manual of Style

5) **PLAGIARISM**

The integrity of academic writing is originality. The author should ensure most of the work and ideas in the essay are generated from knowledge acquired from his original idea or research. However, it is also useful to include contributions by other authors but with the appropriate acknowledgment.

The act of presenting work or idea of another source as your own with or without consent of the original author and including it into your work without full acknowledgment of the original author. It is considered as a fraudulent representation of another person's idea or work without reference to the person. “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34).

6) CONCLUSION

In writing an academic paper, the student or author should have the ability to generate original ideas with the right grammar and punctuation. A standard writing style must be adopted to ensure consistency in formatting, expressions, font style, et cetera. Plagiarism is a crime and must be avoided.

REFERENCES

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